

Ecodesign as a key concept for improving the life cycle environmental performance of proton-exchange membrane fuel cells

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Abstract:

Fuel cell and hydrogen (FCH) technologies are an important part of the energy transition in the EU, therefore the environmental impact assessment of FCH technologies is crucial for further policy decisions. Future FCH production will need to implement ecodesign actions to minimise the environmental impact. The EU-funded project eGHOST defines ecodesign actions for FCH technologies to support the FCH industry. In the case of a proton-exchange membrane fuel cell (PEMFC), four future product concepts are defined together with the associated inventories. For each product concept, a life cycle assessment was carried out and the resultant environmental profiles benchmarked against a reference PEMFC case representing the current state. The study covers the manufacturing and end-of-life phases, with certain materials, such as platinum, being recycled in a closed loop. The results show that environmental impacts can be significantly reduced by implementing ecodesign measures, in the case of climate change by up to 85%. Ecodesign actions related to the reduction of platinum content (lower platinum loading) were identified as top priority, but not the only ones to pay attention to.

Keywords: ecodesign, life cycle assessment, proton-exchange membrane fuel cell, critical raw material, end-of-life, recycling

1 Introduction

The European Union (EU), as one of the six largest emitters of greenhouse gases (GHG) [1], bears great responsibility for climate change. To mitigate climate change, the EU has introduced an ambitious European Green Deal [2] to achieve carbon neutrality by 2050, ensure economic growth decoupled from resource use and ensure that no person or place is left behind. The interim targets for 2030 are defined by the 2030 Climate and Energy Framework [3]. The key targets for 2030 are: (i) reduction of greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% compared to 1990 [4], (ii) share of renewable energy sources by at least 32%, and (iii) improvement of energy efficiency by at least 32.5%. In order to achieve these targets, a transition to a decarbonised energy system is required.

Fuel cell and hydrogen (FCH) technologies have been recognised as one of the crucial elements of this transition, as they can be used in various sectors such as transport, industry and buildings [5]. The transport sector is responsible for 29% of GHG emissions in the EU (and 14% globally [6]), making it

the main contributor to climate change [7]. In order to achieve its targets, the EU must reduce GHG emissions from the transport sector by around 72%, which requires a paradigm shift.

Life cycle assessment (LCA) studies suggest that power-to-hydrogen chains can reduce environmental impacts compared to competing conventional technologies. However, the results are highly case-specific and depend on the technological and methodological choices made in the environmental assessment [8]. Staffell et al. [9] provided a thorough overview of the role of hydrogen and fuel cells in the global energy system and highlighted the role of fuel cell electric vehicles, which predominantly use proton-exchange membrane fuel cells (PEMFCs), in achieving long-term deep decarbonisation. Since the goal of FCH technologies is to reduce the environmental impact compared to current technologies, the LCA methodology is well integrated into hydrogen research. Valente et al. [10] investigated methodological choices in the LCA of hydrogen energy systems. Similarly, other authors conducted a systematic review of the literature on LCA for hydrogen in road transportation [11] and electricity generation [12]. The EU recognises LCA as an integral part of hydrogen research and requires it in many projects funded under the Clean Hydrogen Partnership (the successor to the Fuel Cells and Hydrogen Joint Undertaking, FCH JU) [13]. A thorough review of LCA studies conducted as part of projects established under the Clean Hydrogen Partnership shows that, while the majority of LCAs conducted were of acceptable or good quality, methodologies vary widely and further work is needed to ensure comparability and better interpretation of results [14].

Most research emphasises the importance of the FCH technology use phase (involving, e.g., hydrogen consumption in PEMFCs) in the environmental impact of FCH systems [8,15–18]. However, considering the diverse environmental impacts of fuel cells in vehicles, Simons and Bauer [19] noted that the fuel cells themselves may be more critical to the overall environmental impact than hydrogen production and that there must also be radical changes in technology development to reduce environmental impacts [19]. Several studies confirm the environmental relevance of the manufacturing phase [20–22]. Therefore, it is important to focus on the manufacturing and end-of-life activities in the life cycle of PEMFCs. The most common FCH technology is PEMFC [10], as it is the most mature and currently the only fuel cell alternative to internal combustion engines in the transportation sector. The main advantages of the PEMFC technology for the transportation sector are the low operating temperature, short start-up time, fast refuelling, and the use of solid electrolytes [23,24]. On the other hand, the main disadvantages are the high costs, cold start conditions, and insufficient durability [23,25]. Another problem with PEMFCs is the use of platinum (Pt) in the membrane electrode assembly (MEA). Pt is the main environmental hotspot [19,26–31] of the PEMFC stack and also an economic issue. It accounts for about 50 % of the cost of a PEMFC stack [32]. Therefore, researchers are continuously trying to reduce the need for platinum in FCHs. Although lower Pt loading contributes to a lower environmental impact in the manufacturing phase, some studies suggest that lower Pt loading decreases the efficiency and thus increases the environmental impact during the lifetime of the PEMFC stack [33,34].

With the growing electrification of the transport sector, the annual demand for platinum group metals (PGMs) is expected to increase further [35]. The European Green Deal [2] recognises the importance of resource security to achieve the goal of climate neutrality by 2050. An EU study on critical raw materials (CRM) predicts that global competition for resources will increase over the next decade and lists 34 critical and strategic raw materials in the 2023 study [35]. Some LCA studies focus on critical materials used in FCH technologies [28,29,36], highlighting Pt, Nafion[®], polyether ether ketone (PEEK), polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE), and silicone as critical materials. Zhang et al. [37] also pointed out that the global reserves of PGMs are not sufficient for long-term demand. Due to the scarcity and resource security issues of PGMs, the recycling processes of PGMs from FCH technologies are becoming

increasingly important. Due to the low technology readiness level (TRL), the end-of-life (EoL) stage of PEMFC stacks and other FCH technologies is underdeveloped in most LCA studies [10]. For PEMFCs, material recovery options can be categorised into (i) hydrometallurgical methods and (ii) pyrometallurgical methods [38]. Studies for the two most mature methods show that the environmental benefits of recycling Pt far outweigh the environmental impact of the recycling process [39–42]. While most studies focus on Pt recycling, Valente et al. [43] have shown that the recovery of valuable materials is not limited to PGMs.

The reduction of PGM materials in FCH technologies is also an important aspect in ecodesign, which involves a holistic approach that defines options for sustainable-by-design products that avoid burden shifting across sustainability dimensions [44]. The main goal of ecodesign is to anticipate and minimise environmental impacts without reducing the quality of the product or changing its functionality [45]. Ecodesign is promoted within the EU because it is seen as a complementary method for achieving general sustainability goals [46]. The EU supports ecodesign through a solid legal framework, the Ecodesign Directive 2009/125/EC [47]. The current Ecodesign Directive will soon be replaced by a new regulation [48]. The Council has already adopted its position on the proposed regulation, which will extend the scope to set environmental sustainability requirements for almost all types of goods on the EU market, not limited to energy-related products. The Ecodesign Directive is supported by the Methodology for the Ecodesign of Energy-related Products (MEErP) [49], which uses a free and easy-to-use LCA-based tool – EcoReport. The EcoReport tool is a simplified LCA tool that can be used to carry out an environmental and economic assessment [44]. Updating the EcoReport tool has been suggested in some studies [44,50,51]. Despite the aforementioned EU directive, the literature on the ecodesign of FCH systems is very scarce. In a study by Dumortier and Haussener [52], two design guidelines for hydrogen production using photoelectrochemical water splitting systems were presented in order to reduce the environmental impact. Recently, Ansaloni et al. [53] used the Ecodesign Strategy Wheel to develop different design scenarios for hydrogen-powered passenger ships.

Within this context, this study presents the ecodesign of a PEMFC stack for automotive applications, using the Ecodesign Strategy Wheel together with LCA to define and assess relevant ecodesign actions in the framework of the EU-funded project eGHOST, which has established a first milestone in ecodesign criteria in the European hydrogen sector. The objectives of the project were: (i) development of an FCH ecodesign methodology, (ii) subsequent contribution to European initiatives, and (iii) formulation of ecodesign guidelines for FCH products. The eGHOST project has developed two specific ecodesign guidelines, one for PEMFC stacks and one for solid oxide electrolysis cell stacks [54]. Moreover, the lessons learned and all the results of the project are summarised in the eGHOST White Book [55]. With the valuable input from industry and other relevant stakeholders within the eGHOST project, four product concepts with different scenarios of ecodesign actions were defined in addition to the reference case, involving one 48 kW_e PEMFC stack, which is a further work beyond the study by Mori et al. [26], where the life cycle sustainability assessment of (only) the reference case was conducted. Hence, the previous study was enriched herein by introducing product concepts and their novel life cycle inventories, which are a result of ecodesign actions that address not only manufacturing but also EoL strategies for the PEMFC stack in open and closed-loop recycling schemes. The product concepts were evaluated using LCA to demonstrate the potential reduction in environmental impacts and the importance of a circular economy approach that includes the recycling of critical materials. In addition to closed-loop recycling, open-loop recycling was applied, which manifests itself in potentially avoided environmental impacts when using recovered materials on the market. In order to transparently present the impacts of closed-loop and open-loop recycling, a closed-loop recycling & reuse phase was introduced along the manufacturing phase and the EoL phase. The combined

manufacturing and EoL approach in this ecodesign study was feasible thanks to the synergy between two projects funded by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership, leading to a knowledge transfer regarding ecodesign actions set in eGHOST [54] and the use of the recycling process of Pt from the BEST4Hy project [56], whose overall objective is to increase the TRL of recycling technologies adapted specifically to PEMFCs and solid oxide fuel cells maximising the recycling of critical raw materials (PGMs, rare earth elements, cobalt, and nickel) and including economic and environmental evaluation.

2 Methodology

Two methodologies were used in this study, namely ecodesign, in which the ecodesign strategy wheel approach was used for targeted brainstorming sessions with experts from industry, university and research institutes within the eGHOST project, and the LCA methodology for assessing potential environmental impacts of product systems.

2.1 Ecodesign methodology

The methodology of ecodesign is both a principle and an approach. It incorporates environmental considerations into the design and development of products. The main objective of ecodesign is to anticipate and minimise negative impacts on the environment (during the production phase, the use phase, and at the end of a product's life cycle) [45]. The current Ecodesign Directive 2009/125/EC [47] has proven to be beneficial for businesses, consumers, and the environment. Ecodesign, by aiming at more durable, repairable, upgradeable, and modular products, also supports the recycling of materials (especially CRMs), addressing growing concerns associated with their extraction and low recirculation rates.

The ecodesign strategy wheel, proposed by Brezet et al. [57] and presented in Figure 1, is a common generic approach to ecodesign, which was used as a preliminary guidance. It defines the most common ecodesign measures on different levels: product component level, product structure level, and product system level, while also referring to the life-cycle stages to which they must relate. The product levels further divide to sub-level actions:

- i. **Product Component Level**, with sub-level actions:
 1. Selection of low-impact materials (axis 1).
 2. Reduction of materials used (axis 2).
- ii. **Product Structure Level**, with sub-level actions:
 3. Optimisation of production techniques (axis 3).
 4. Optimisation of the distribution system (axis 4).
 5. Reduction of impacts during the use phase of a product (axis 5).
- iii. **Product System Level**, with sub-level actions:
 6. Optimisation of operating system lifetime (axis 6).
 7. Optimisation of the EoL system (axis 7).

Although the ecodesign methodology includes all life cycle phases, the study implemented only actions relevant to the manufacturing and EoL phase, due to the scope of the study. Nevertheless, it should be acknowledged that some indirect effects of the implemented actions can occur in the use phase, but they are out of the scope of the study. It should also be noted that the ecodesign actions in this study would not influence the performance of the product, meaning that the functionality, durability, and efficiency of the product stay (at least) the same with the implementation of ecodesign actions. Therefore, within the strategy wheel, the focus of the study was placed on the product component level, combining the use of low-impact materials and the reduction of materials used (which is also relevant to the EoL strategy). In this regard, the identification of low-impact materials took into consideration the goal and scope of the study and was determined by literature review or LCA, and the

reduction of materials used was approached in a quantitative way (i.e. quantitative reduction of the material).

Figure 1: Ecodesign strategy wheel with all axes of possible product improvements, based on [57]

Following the ecodesign strategy wheel, different ecodesign actions for the PEMFC technology, with different time frames (short term, medium term, and long term) and on each ecodesign axis, were proposed. Based on the identified ecodesign actions, four product concepts were proposed for the PEMFC stack, which are presented in detail in the next section.

2.2 Product concepts of the PEMFC stack

Four product concepts were defined based on the reference 48 kW_e PEMFC stack:

- Short-term product concept* is based on short-term actions that are expected to be realised and implemented in the near future.
- Long-term product concept* includes medium-to-long term ecodesign actions that are expected to be implemented in the future.
- Optimistic product concept* is the concept already under implementation by some top-end technological companies and/or developed at the laboratory scale.
- Disruptive product concept* includes actions that are still under development or in the early research or even conceptual phase.

The product concepts are a result of the eGHOST project [54]. The PEMFC reference product on which ecodesign actions are implemented is presented in detail in Mori et al. [26]. The reference Pt loading of the PEMFC stack is 0.465 mg Pt/cm². The ecodesign actions contained in the product concepts are summarised in Table 1 and described in detail in Table 2. Each subsequent product concept contains ecodesign actions that have already been implemented in the previous product concepts. In Table 1,

an “X” indicates that the new ecodesign action has been implemented or that the already implemented ecodesign action has been improved (e.g. higher recycling rate).

Table 1: Ecodesign actions implemented in each product concept

Ecodesign actions	Product concepts	Short-term concept	Long-term concept	Optimistic concept	Disruptive concept
Action 1.1 – Use of recycled Pt		X		X	X
Action 1.4 – Reuse of endplates		X			
Action 2.1 – Reduction of Pt loading		X	X	X	
Action 2.2 – Optimisation of the triple phase boundary		X	X	X	
Action 2.3 – Mass reduction of various materials		X	X	X	X
Action 5 – Reuse of BPP			X	X	X
Action 7 – Use of recycled ionomer and copper				X	X

Table 2 quantifies the ecodesign actions in relation to the reference case. All actions are labelled with a specific number (e.g. 1.1), where the first number indicates the relevant axis and the number following the dot represents the sequential number of the action on a specific axis (respecting the order set in eGHOST [54]). Furthermore, the inventories of all product concepts can be defined on the basis of the ecodesign actions listed in Table 2 and the detailed descriptions of product concepts that follow.

2.2.1 Short-term product concept

The short-term ecodesign actions address two ecodesign strategy wheel axes. Within axis 1 (low-impact materials), ecodesign action 1.1 is included, which deals with the use of recycled Pt. Although the recycling of Pt from PEMFC stacks is still at a low TRL, a closed-loop recycling strategy is adopted according to the recycling process from BEST4Hy [56], as it shows promising results for quick development and commercial use. As part of the short-term product concept, a proportion of 30% recycled Pt is expected based on practices in the automotive sector [58]. Axis 1 also includes ecodesign action 1.4, which anticipates 30% reuse of the endplates after sufficient conditioning (which includes washing of the endplates, where no chemicals are needed, but only energy and water).

Within axis 2 (reduction of material consumption), the ecodesign actions include reducing the mass of Pt, bipolar plate (BPP), gas diffusion layer (GDL), and PFSA (perfluorosulfonic acid) membrane. Ecodesign action 2.1 concerns the reduction of the Pt loading from 0.465 mg Pt/cm² (reference case) to 0.235 mg Pt/cm² (reduction of 49%). The reduction of Pt loading is feasible, and some options are already commercially available [34]. The reduction in Pt loading can be achieved in two ways. Primarily, by optimising pure Pt particles: (i) research shows that small and homogeneous particles with narrow size distribution have the potential to balance performance and durability [59], and (ii) different geometries and electronic states of different crystal faces of nanoparticles have different catalytic properties for the same reaction, and the surface structure of metal catalysts can be achieved by controlling the shape of metal nanoparticles [60]. Secondly, Pt alloys can be used to increase the mass activity, which is due to the lattice strain of the platinum skin surface formed by the surface dealloying and the modified electronic structure that weakens the interaction between the atoms on the Pt surface and the intermediate species [59]. At the same time, the amount of Pt in the catalytic particles is reduced, resulting in a lower overall Pt loading. In the study, the first way of reduction of Pt loading was considered. Ecodesign action 2.2 anticipates the optimisation of the triple-phase boundary. With the improved electrochemical reaction, which is due to the more homogeneous distribution of the Pt particles, the output power increases by 5%, which increases the power-to-mass ratio. In addition, ecodesign action 2.3 deals with the reduction of the mass of the various materials. The thickness of the PFSA membrane is reduced by 30%, that of the BPP by 15%, and that of the GDL by 45%.

2.2.2 Long-term product concept

In the long-term product concept, the Pt loading is reduced to 0.220 mg Pt/cm² (ecodesign action 2.1), the BPP is additionally reduced by 20%, the GDL by 18% and the PFSA membrane by 16% (ecodesign action 2.3). In addition, ecodesign action 2.2 is implemented, which anticipates a further increase in power density from 1.66 to 2.46 kW/kg (48% increase). The ecodesign action within axis 5 (low impact during the use phase) is also included, which deals with refurbishment strategies for FCH systems. The BPPs that are not yet excessively degraded could be refurbished and reused. The long-term product concept envisages the reuse of 30% of the BPPs.

Table 2: Ecodesign action quantification related to the reference case

Quantified Ecodesign actions	Short-term	Long-term	Optimistic	Disruptive
Rate of recycled Pt used (1.1)	30%	30%	70%	95%
Rate of endplates reuse (1.4)	30%	30%	30%	30%
Rate of Pt use reduction (2.1)*	-49%	-53%	-73%	-81%
Power/mass ratio increase (2.2)*	+14%	+81%	+96%	+184%
Rate of BPP use reduction (2.3)*	-15%	-47%	-52%	-69%
Rate of GDL use reduction (2.3)*	-45%	-70%	-72%	-79%
Rate of Nafion® use reduction (2.3)*	-30%	-62%	-71%	-76%
Rate of BPP reuse (5)	/	30%	67%	80%
Rate of recycled copper used (7)	/	/	/	80%
Rate of recycled Nafion® used (7)	/	/	30%	95%

*Note: Rates of material reductions and power/mass ratio increase are relative to the reference case

2.2.3 Optimistic product concept

The optimistic product concept includes all ecodesign actions foreseen in the long-term product concept unless the new actions perform better in the same aspect. The use of recycled Pt is increased to 70% (ecodesign action 1.1). The Pt loading is reduced to 0.125 mg Pt/cm² (ecodesign action 2.1), the BPP is additionally reduced by 10% and the PFSA membrane by 20% (ecodesign action 2.3). It is assumed that the redesign of the system can increase the power-to-mass ratio by 5% (ecodesign action 2.2). The reuse rate of BPPs is also increased to 67% (ecodesign action 5). In addition, the ecodesign action within axis 7 (EoL optimisation) is introduced, which concerns the recycling of PFSA membranes. Recent developments in the field of FCH-relevant recycling technologies suggest that it will be possible to achieve a high closed-loop recycling rate of Pt and to recycle other valuable materials such as the ionomer (PFSA). The optimistic concept envisages the use of 30% recycled ionomer. The ionomer recycling process is also being developed in the BEST4Hy project, but at a lower TRL than Pt recycling, and was adopted in this study for ionomer recycling.

2.2.4 Disruptive product concept

The use of recycled Pt is increased to 95% (ecodesign action 1.1), as some laboratory tests indicate that a recycling rate of 95% is possible [61]. The BPP is additionally reduced by 20%, and the GDL by 11%. The mass of the endplates (glass fibre reinforced thermoplastic, GRTP) is also reduced by 30% (ecodesign action 2.3). The reuse rate of BPP is increased to 80% (ecodesign action 5). In addition, the rate of recycled ionomer is increased to 95%. Ecodesign action 7 concerns the recycling of copper from current collectors. In the disruptive product concept, it was assumed that 80% of the copper can be recycled in a closed loop, which means that the disruptive product concept contains 80% recycled copper.

2.3 LCA methodology

The standardised LCA methodology defined in ISO 14040 [62] and ISO 14044 [63] was considered in the study, in addition to the guidelines of the International Reference Life Cycle Data System (ILCD) [64] and FC-HyGuide [65,66]. The LCA methodology consists of four interrelated phases: (i) goal and

scope, (ii) life cycle inventory (LCI) analysis, (iii) life cycle impact assessment (LCIA), and (iv) interpretation of results. All LCA models were created using the LCA for Experts 10.7 software [67], previously known as GaBi.

2.3.1 Goal and scope

The main goal of the study is to assess the potential environmental impacts of each product concept, and thus to evaluate the environmental suitability of the aforementioned ecodesign actions in the manufacturing and EoL phase of a 48 kW_e PEMFC stack used in a light commercial vehicle for passenger transportation. One 48 kW_e PEMFC stack also represents the functional unit of the study. The system boundaries of the PEMFC stack include the following components: MEA, gaskets, BPP, endplates, current collectors, and connecting components. The scope of the study is “cradle-to-grave”, including manufacturing and EoL of the PEMFC stack while excluding its use [54]. The use phase is excluded to keep focus on the target product (PEMFC stack). Since the use phase is expected to be the most influential one [8,15–17], the focus of the study would move from the PEMFC stack to the hydrogen fuel if the use phase was included.

2.3.2 Life cycle inventory

The LCI of the reference case was prepared on the basis of the technical specifications provided by the industrial partner in the eGHOST project [26]. The novel LCIs for all aforementioned PEMFC product concepts were derived from the reference case with the application of the specific ecodesign actions as defined in Table 2. The LCIs are presented separately for the manufacturing phase (Table 3) and the EoL phase (Table 4). While the LCIs for the manufacturing phase were based on the bill of materials (reference case) and the applied ecodesign actions (product concepts), the LCIs for the EoL phase were defined using ecodesign actions together with current and future EoL processes. If the material is recyclable, then recycling was selected as an EoL process. For non-recyclable materials (e.g. silicone) either landfilling or incineration can be chosen since both are feasible. It should be noted that Table 4 shows the input material flows with EoL processes defined based on current EoL technologies. All materials from the PEMFC stack after the manual dismantling process are included in the EoL phase.

Due to the improvements of the product concepts, which also lead to an enhanced performance, the LCI of each product concept was normalised to 48 kW_e, so that a direct comparison was possible according to the functional unit defined in the study. The databases ecoinvent 3.9 [68] and Sphera [69] were used as the source of background data. In the case of ionomer, an inventory model of the Nafion[®] production process with only elementary flows was used.

Table 3: Life cycle inventories of the manufacturing phase of the PEMFC stack reference case and product concepts (values per functional unit)

Component	Material	Reference	Short-term	Long-term	Optimistic	Disruptive
Pt/C	Pt – virgin [g]	26	9.1	8.4	2.1	0.25
	Pt – recycled [g]	/	3.9	3.6	4.9	4.75
	Carbon black [g]	39	37	24	23	19
Ionomer	PFSA – virgin [g]	144	101	55	29	1.8
	PFSA – recycled [g]	/	/	/	13	33
/	Water [g]	490	467	307	293	240
/	Alcohol [g]	220	210	138	131	108
Subgasket	PEN/PET film [g]	1820	1733	1142	1087	891
Carbon cloths fibre	Carbon cloth fibre [g]	1249	687	370	352	257
BPP	Stainless steel – virgin [g]	21623	18379	7974	3436	1352
	Stainless steel – reused [g]	/	/	3418	6871	5408
Gasket	Silicone [g]	1265	1204	793	755	619
Endplate	G RTP – virgin [g]	3800	2533	1668	1589	912
	G RTP – reused [g]	/	1086	715	681	391
Current collector	Copper – virgin [g]	950	905	596	567	93
	Copper – recycled [g]	/	/	/	/	372
Connecting components	Chromium steel [g]	852	811	534	509	417
	Steel [g]	2820	2686	1769	1684	1381
Electricity [kWh]	/	410	391	257	245	201
PEMFC stack [g]		34588	30175	19070	17603	12152

Table 4: Life cycle inventory of the end-of-life phase of the PEMFC stack reference case and product concepts (values per functional unit)

Component	Material	EoL process	Reference	Short-term	Long-term	Optimistic	Disruptive
Connecting components	Chromium steel [g]	Open-loop recycling	852	811	534	509	417
	Steel [g]	Open-loop recycling	2820	2686	1769	1684	1381
Current collector	Copper [g]	Open-loop recycling	950	905	596	567	93
		Closed-loop recycling	/	/	/	/	372
Endplate	G RTP [g]	Open-loop recycling	3800	2533	1668	1589	912
		Reuse	/	1086	715	681	391
Gasket	Silicone [g]	Landfilling	1265	1204	793	755	619
BPP	Stainless steel [g]	Open-loop recycling	21623	18379	7974	3436	1352
		Reuse	/	/	3418	6871	5408
MEA [g]		Incineration & landfilling	3278	/	/	/	/
		Recycling – BEST4Hy	/	2571	1603	1511	1207

2.3.3 Life cycle impact assessment

The Environmental Footprint (EF) 3.1 was selected as the LCIA method for assessing the environmental impacts. 16 environmental impact categories from various LCIA methods are included in the EF 3.1 method. The analysis comprises seven of these categories, which are shown in Table 5. The selected environmental impact categories are in line with the FC-HyGuide guidelines [65,66] and previous studies in the field [26]. Although the remaining indicators within the EF3.1 method (ionising radiation, ozone depletion, particulate matter, land use, water use, etc.) could also be directly considered, the implementation of multiple environmental indicators could jeopardise the identification and interpretation of sustainability-oriented design actions, and thus the formulation and prioritisation of new eco-designed product concepts. EF 3.1 is regularly updated by the European Commission to ensure a balance between providing a robust methodology and incorporating the latest scientific developments [70].

Table 5: Impact categories within EF 3.1 used in the study [70]

Impact category	Indicator	Unit
Acidification	Accumulated Exceedance	mol H ⁺ _{eq}
Climate change	Radiative forcing as Global Warming Potential (GWP100)	kg CO _{2eq}
Eutrophication – freshwater	Fraction of nutrients reaching freshwater end compartment (P)	kg P _{eq}
Eutrophication – marine	Fraction of nutrients reaching marine end compartment (N)	kg N _{eq}
Eutrophication – terrestrial	Accumulated Exceedance	mol N _{eq}
Resource use – fossils	Abiotic resource depletion – fossil fuels (ADP fossil)	MJ
Resource use – minerals & metals	Abiotic resource depletion (ADP ultimate reserves)	kg Sb _{eq}

2.4 LCA model

The LCA model (Figure 2) for the PEMFC stack reference case and ecodesigned product concepts comprises the following life cycle phases: manufacturing, closed-loop recycling & reuse, and EoL. The closed-loop recycling & reuse phase was additionally defined due to the fact that closed-loop recycled materials and reused components could be included both in the manufacturing phase and in the EoL phase. In addition, the model was structured to allow an assessment of the potential avoided impacts resulting from open-loop recycling, where materials can be used in the materials market as recovered (recycled) materials. The transportation of materials or components to the manufacturing or EoL site and the operating phase were not included in the model as they are outside the scope of the ecodesign actors.

In the manufacturing phase, most components only include raw material extraction, as no specific manufacturing data is available. On the other hand, some generic components are available in databases, which means that they also include manufacturing processes. If possible, this generic data was used for components. Otherwise, the manufacturing processes were only considered as an estimate of the total electricity consumption for the production of PEMFC stacks. In addition, net masses of the materials were considered in the study. These assumptions have a negligible influence given the main objective of the study, which is to demonstrate the environmental suitability of ecodesign actions in PEMFC technology with respect to the reference case. In this regard, the same assumptions were included in the reference case and in all product concepts.

The closed-loop recycling & reuse phase includes the generic recycling processes available in generic databases, conditioning of reused components, and the aggregated recycling process for recovered Pt and PFSA membranes with inventory from the BEST4Hy project [71]. The closed-loop recycling process is possible only for materials which do not lose mechanical properties in comparison to the virgin materials. If the recycling process degrades the materials too much, the recycled materials cannot be used in the same applications and an open-loop recycling was proposed. The reuse is possible for components which still hold the technical abilities and can be used again with minor conditioning (e.g. cleaning).

Open-loop recycling means that the recycled material is not used in the same application, but it goes to the market and is used in other industries. The EoL phase includes open-loop recycling, landfilling, and incineration of materials/components. For environmental assessment, generic processes from databases were used. For open-loop recycling, emissions which occur in the recycling process are included in the EoL phase. The credit from open-loop recycling is outside the system boundaries of the PEMFC stack manufacturing and EoL phase, but considered within the avoided impacts. Avoided impacts represent the potential reduction due to the use of open-loop recycled materials in other industries and therefore lower global usage of virgin materials. Every open-loop recycling process contributes to some avoided impacts, but these are not included in the results unless otherwise stated. The closed-loop recycling and reuse process does not have 100% closed-loop or reuse ratio, meaning

that materials/components go to open-loop recycling. Even in the disruptive case, the closed-loop and reuse ratios never reach 100%.

Figure 2: LCA model for the PEMFC stack long-term concept

The geographical location of the processes used from databases is, if possible, Europe. Otherwise, Germany or the global geographical location were used. The European electricity mix is used in all cases where electricity is consumed.

3 Results and discussion

In this section, the results of the LCA are presented first, followed by the identification of hotspots and the analysis of the reduction of the environmental impacts of product concepts. The analysis also highlights the specific ecodesign actions that contribute most to the reduction of environmental impacts.

3.1 Environmental impacts of the ecodesigned product concepts

The environmental impacts of the 48 kW_e PEMFC stack reference case and the ecodesigned product concepts are presented in Table 6, where the absolute values of the total environmental impacts are given, and in Figure 3, where relative environmental impacts of product concepts compared to the reference case are given. Further analysis of the climate change and freshwater eutrophication impact categories is presented in Figure 4 and Figure 5, where the detailed results of the contribution of the life cycle stages, the relative reduction, and the potential relative reduction associated with avoided impacts are shown for the reference case and the product concepts. A graphical presentation of the results of other impact categories is given in the Supplementary Information. Overall, the results confirm the suitability of the ecodesigned product concepts, as further detailed in Section 3.2.

Table 6: Environmental impacts of the PEMFC stack reference case and the ecodesigned product concepts

Impact category	Reference	Short-term	Long-term	Optimistic	Disruptive
Acidification [mol H ⁺ _{eq}]	3.31E+01	1.31E+01	1.13E+01	3.36E+00	8.79E-01
Climate change - total [kg CO _{2eq}]	1.21E+03	8.38E+02	5.84E+02	3.19E+02	1.84E+02
Eutrophication, freshwater [kg P _{eq}]	5.24E-03	6.21E-03	3.95E-03	3.50E-03	2.51E-03
Eutrophication, marine [kg N _{eq}]	1.53E+00	7.51E-01	5.96E-01	2.44E-01	1.13E-01
Eutrophication, terrestrial [mol N _{eq}]	1.65E+01	7.95E+00	6.35E+00	2.51E+00	1.14E+00
Resource use, fossils [MJ]	1.27E+04	8.76E+03	6.26E+03	3.46E+03	2.14E+03
Resource use, minerals and metals [kg Sb _{eq}]	5.76E-02	2.61E-02	2.00E-02	6.98E-03	1.78E-03

As shown in Figure 3, ecodesign actions can lead to a significant reduction in resource use and all environmental impact indicators. Each impact category, with the exception of freshwater eutrophication, shows similar reductions for each product concept. The reductions are lower for the short-term product concepts: from 31% (climate change and fossil resource use) to 60% (acidification). The reductions in environmental impacts are higher for every other product concept. For the disruptive product concept, reductions from 83% (fossil resource use) to 97% (acidification and use of minerals & metals) were found. The freshwater eutrophication impact category is the only case in which the total environmental impact for the product concept was found to be higher than for the reference case, which only applies to the short-term concept. This is mainly due to Pt recycling, more specifically to the use of ammonium chloride in the hydrometallurgical process.

Figure 3: Relative environmental impacts of product concepts compared to the reference case

The bars in the diagrams in Figure 4 and Figure 5 are divided into life cycle stages, each of which is colour-coded in the legend. The relative values in the upper blue frames represent the relative

reductions of the individual product concept compared to the reference case without taking the avoided impacts into account. The relative values in the lower green frames represent the potential relative reduction of the total impacts if the avoided impacts associated with open-loop recycling are considered. The figures show a leading role of the manufacturing phase. Nevertheless, as further detailed in Sections 3.3 and 3.4, the role played by the remaining stages and the avoided impacts associated with open-loop recycling should not be neglected.

Figure 4: Contribution of life cycle stages to the climate change impact category

Figure 5: Contribution of life cycle stages to the freshwater eutrophication impact category

3.2 The impact of ecodesign actions on environmental impact indicators

In order to better understand the reduction of the environmental impact indicators at the product concept level, the reductions of the environmental impact indicators attributable to the individual ecodesign actions for the long-term PEMFC product concept were evaluated separately. It is important to note that the order of implementation of ecodesign action is important when two different ecodesign actions target the same material or component (e.g. 1.1 and 2.1 both target Pt). The order of the ecodesign actions follows the ecodesign strategy wheel, i.e. ecodesign action 1.1 is implemented first, ecodesign action 1.5 second and so on. The results of the reduction of the environmental impact indicators associated with the implementation of each ecodesign action are shown in Figure 6. Ecodesign actions were found to contribute similarly to the total reduction in all impact categories

except freshwater eutrophication. A more detailed illustration of the contribution of the ecodesign actions to the total reductions for climate change is shown in Figure 7, and for freshwater eutrophication in Figure 8. Diagrams for the other impact categories under study are included in the Supplementary Information.

Figure 6: Contribution of ecodesign actions to reducing environmental impacts in the long-term PEMFC product concept (impacts relative to the reference case)

Regardless of the order in which the ecodesign actions are implemented, the greatest reduction in environmental impact indicators was found to be achieved by ecodesign action 2.1 (reducing Pt loading). In the case of climate change, this action reduces climate change by 29% relative to the reference case. Ecodesign actions 1.1 (use of recycled Pt) and 2.3 (reduction of material mass) also play an important role, as they reduce climate change by 10.4% and 11.1%, respectively. If ecodesign action 2.3 was implemented before ecodesign action 1.1, action 2.3 would reduce climate change by 35% and action 1.1 by 5%. In both cases, the total reduction in climate change would be the same and would reach the same absolute value after the implementation of ecodesign actions. The remaining ecodesign actions were gathered under “Rest” as they contribute a negligible share to the total environmental reductions, except for the freshwater eutrophication and use of minerals & metals categories.

When compared to the preliminary findings in the previous study by Mori et al. [26], where Pt loading and Pt recycling played a similar role in environmental impacts reduction, the results of the present enriched study indicate that Pt loading reduction would play a leading role.

Figure 7: Contribution of ecodesign actions to climate change for the long-term PEMFC product concept (reductions relative to the reference case)

In the case of freshwater eutrophication, the ecodesign action 1.1 increases the impact by 20% relative to the reference case. The increase in ecodesign action 1.1 is due to the increased use of recycled Pt, being the Pt recycling process the main hotspot for freshwater eutrophication. On the other hand, ecodesign action 2.1 reduces freshwater eutrophication by 12% while ecodesign action 2.3 only by 1%. The largest reduction in freshwater eutrophication was found to be achieved by the rest of ecodesign actions (32% reduction). In particular, the largest contribution would be linked to ecodesign action 2.2, which increases the power-to-mass ratio and thus reduces the mass of GRTP, the main hotspot in terms of freshwater eutrophication. If ecodesign action 2.1 were implemented before ecodesign action 1.1, freshwater eutrophication would be reduced by 1%, and action 1.1 would increase freshwater eutrophication by 9%.

Figure 8: Contribution of ecodesign actions to freshwater eutrophication for the long-term PEMFC product concept (reductions relative to the reference case)

3.3 Hotspot analysis

As shown in Figure 4, Figure 5, and supplementary information, according to the scope of the study, the manufacturing phase is the most important hotspot for each impact category and each product concept. The manufacturing phase as a hotspot is most dominant in the reference case, where it accounts for 98-99% of the environmental impacts, except for the use of minerals & metals category, where the manufacturing phase accounts for 93% (Table 7). As for the role of the manufacturing phase in the environmental profile of the product concepts, there are greater differences between the environmental impacts than in the reference case. In the short-term product concept, the shares linked to manufacturing range from 64% (freshwater eutrophication) to 93% (acidification); from 66% (freshwater eutrophication) to 95% (acidification) in the long-term product concept (Table 8); from 66% (climate change and fossil resource use) to 89% (acidification) in the optimistic product concept; and from 53% (climate change) to 67% (acidification) in the disruptive product concept. The lowest shares of the manufacturing phase for the disruptive product concept are linked to the highest rates of closed-loop recycled materials and reused components. The high proportions of closed-loop recycled materials and reused components also reduce the share of environmental impacts for the EoL phase. On average, it falls from 15% in the short-term product concept to 6% in the disruptive product concept. In contrast, the contribution of closed-loop recycling & reuse increases from 7% in the short-term concept to 34% in the disruptive product concept.

Table 7: Relative shares of life cycle phases in the environmental profile of the PEMFC reference case

Impact category	Manufacturing phase	Reuse & closed-loop recycling	End-of-life
Acidification	98.7%	0%	1.3%
Climate change	98.2%	0%	1.8%
Eutrophication, freshwater	98.2%	0%	1.8%
Eutrophication, marine	98.5%	0%	1.5%
Eutrophication, terrestrial	98.5%	0%	1.5%
Resource use, fossils	98.8%	0%	1.2%
Resource use, minerals and metals	92.6%	0%	7.4%

The environmental impacts of the EoL and closed-loop recycling & reuse phases are mainly due to the energy consumption for recycling or reuse. Conventional EoL processes, such as landfilling, were not found to have a major impact on the selected environmental indicators. On average, the EoL phase contributes only 2% to the total environmental impacts in the reference case. It should be noted that only virgin materials are used in the reference case, which generally involve higher environmental impacts.

Table 8: Relative shares of life cycle phases in the environmental of the long-term PEMFC product concept

Impact category	Manufacturing phase	Reuse & closed-loop recycling	End-of-life
Acidification	95.3%	1.2%	3.5%
Climate change	76.2%	8.6%	15.3%
Eutrophication, freshwater	65.8%	12.7%	21.5%
Eutrophication, marine	87.5%	4.2%	8.3%
Eutrophication, terrestrial	87.7%	4.1%	8.2%
Resource use, fossils	75.8%	8.9%	15.3%
Resource use, minerals and metals	90.7%	0.0%	9.2%

Additional analysis regarding hotspot identification within the manufacturing phase was made for the climate change indicator. Under this indicator, MEA was identified as the main hotspot in this key phase as it would account for 78% of the climate change impact in the reference case and 72% in the long-term product concept. The second largest hotspot was found to be the production process itself (11% for the reference case and 17% for the long-term product concept), which is closely linked to the required electricity. In this regard, changes in the electricity mix could significantly affect this finding, but this kind of analysis is out of the scope of the study. The same would apply to the recycling of Pt and ionomer in the EoL phase, where a different electricity mix could also importantly affect the results.

3.4 Potential avoided impacts

In this study, avoided impacts refer to potentially avoided environmental impacts that would occur if the recovered materials were used on the market. The avoided environmental impacts were calculated as the difference between the environmental impacts of the virgin material and the environmental impacts of the recovered material. The avoided impacts are presented separately and are not included in the total environmental impacts of the reference case or product concepts. Nevertheless, it is important to highlight the potential for additional environmental impact reduction of PEMFC technologies in the open-loop concepts. As presented in Table 9, the highest avoided impacts were found in the short-term product concept, since most of the Pt (and other materials) would be sent for open-loop recycling. In the following product concepts, the proportion of open-loop recycling is lower, which reduces the potentially avoided impacts.

In the reference case, stainless steel would contribute the most to the avoided impacts in all environmental indicators (67% on average), except in freshwater eutrophication, where GRTP would contribute the most (97%). For the short-term concept, Pt arose as the main contributor to the avoided impacts (73% on average), except again in freshwater eutrophication, where GRTP would contribute 95%. In this case, Pt highly contributes to the avoided impacts since the Pt recycling rate is higher than the rate of used recycled Pt in the short-term PEMFC product concept. The long-term and optimistic product concepts were found to involve a similar performance: GRTP – freshwater eutrophication (96% for long-term and 98% for optimistic), and Pt – all other indicators (82% for long-term and 57% for optimistic, on average). In the disruptive product concept, GRTP was found to contribute most to the avoided impact not only in terms of freshwater eutrophication, but also in terms of marine

eutrophication (49%) and use of fossil resources (65%); for other indicators, stainless steel was identified as the key contributor (55% on average).

Table 9: Potential for further reduction of environmental impacts through avoided impacts associated with open-loop recycling

Impact category	Reference	Short-term	Long-term	Optimistic	Disruptive
Acidification	-3%	-43%	-43%	-33%	-19%
Climate change	-10%	-34%	-39%	-21%	-11%
Eutrophication, freshwater	-61%	-35%	-36%	-38%	-30%
Eutrophication, marine	-7%	-55%	-57%	-37%	-19%
Eutrophication, terrestrial	-6%	-54%	-57%	-35%	-15%
Resource use, fossils	-12%	-40%	-44%	-25%	-13%
Resource use, mineral and metals	-15%	-73%	-73%	-72%	-62%

4 Conclusions

In this study, the ecodesign strategy wheel was applied to the PEMFC technology, specifically to a 48 kW_e PEMFC stack for automotive applications. Ecodesign actions at the level of product concept, product structure and product system were defined on the basis of the state of the art and the involvement of experts from industry and research. Applying the ecodesign actions, novel inventories of four future product concepts were progressively defined based on a reference PEMFC stack. The life cycle assessment methodology was used to assess the life cycle environmental profile of all product concepts considered. The most important messages are:

- Ecodesign product concepts were quantified according to the expected development of FCH technology in the industry (short- and long-term product concepts), with an optimistic concept defined as the best possible concept using current FCH technology and a disruptive product concept defined as a breakthrough change in FCH technology development.
- Ecodesign actions can achieve considerable reductions in all environmental impact categories. In the climate change impact category, a reduction of 31% could be achieved for the short-term concept, 52% for the long-term concept, 74% for the optimistic concept, and 85% for the disruptive concept compared to the reference case. Similar or even higher reductions in environmental impacts could be achieved for other indicators. The greatest reductions were found in the acidification category.
- The results for freshwater eutrophication differ slightly. In the short-term concept, freshwater eutrophication could increase by 19% due to the Pt recycling process. Nevertheless, a reduction would be achieved in the other product concepts. In particular, a 52% reduction could be achieved in the disruptive product concept.
- The most important ecodesign action, for all impact categories except freshwater eutrophication, is ecodesign action 2.1: reduction of Pt loading. On average, it is responsible for 54% of the total reduction in the impact categories.
- The most important life cycle hotspot according to the scope of the study is the manufacturing phase. In the reference case, its share is 98% on average, and 60% in the disruptive product concept. The shares linked to the EoL phase generally decrease with each product concept, while the shares linked to closed-loop & reuse increase. This is due to the higher proportion of closed-loop recycling and reuse in the optimistic and disruptive concepts.
- When additionally considering the avoided impacts associated with open-loop recycling, climate change could be additionally reduced by 34% in the short-term concept and by 11% in the disruptive concept. The percentages are even higher for other impact categories.

As future work, additional sensitivity analysis regarding aspects such as electricity mixes and other ecodesign actions is suggested, as well as the study of the impact of ecodesign actions on the use phase. Furthermore, the extension of the LCA study to the economic and social dimensions is recommended.

Overall, it is very important to integrate the ecodesign strategy into the development of FCH technologies in order to (i) achieve lower environmental impacts in the manufacturing phase of FCH technologies; (ii) encourage the FCH industry to produce environmentally-friendly technologies; (iii) encourage the recycling industry to incorporate FCH technologies into day-to-day operations; and (iv) support the EU in creating a sustainable FCH economy that meets all critical material use plans that will be crucial to achieving the goals of giga-scale deployment of FCH technologies.

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